

EFFECTS OF PROSTAGLANDIN ANALOG THERAPY ON THE OCULAR SURFACE OF GLAUCOMA PATIENTS

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Abstract

Objectives: To ascertain how prostaglandin analog treatment affects glaucoma patients' ocular surfaces.

Study design: Cross-sectional

Settings: Armed Forces Institute of Ophthalmology, Rawalpindi.

Duration: January 2025 to June 2025.

Materials and Procedures: Patients who were above the age of eighteen and taking topical PG analogue monotherapy for glaucoma without a h/o glaucoma surgery, including laser treatments and/or minimally invasive glaucoma surgery, were eligible. Therefore, patients undergoing dual or triple therapy were not included. The baseline tear break-up time for each patient was less than 6 seconds. During the trial time, patients were advised not to apply any additional topical drops. Baseline measurements of tear break-up time, inferior corneal staining, and the ocular surface disease index were documented in the same examination room on each visit.

Results: The 40 eyes under study had a mean TBUT of 2.02 ± 0.71 seconds before beginning prostaglandin analog therapy. Eight weeks following the therapy, this rose to 6.34 ± 1.31 seconds ($p < 0.001$). The staining of inferior corneas dropped from 2.40 ± 0.87 to 1.38 ± 0.59 ($p < 0.001$). The initial OSDI reading was 26.31 ± 8.25 and 16.56 ± 6.19 eight weeks after prostaglandin analog therapy. The baseline intraocular pressure (IOP) levels (14.05 ± 2.78 mmHg) and those measured after prostaglandin analog treatment (13.95 ± 3.04 , $p = 0.88$) did not exhibit a statistically significant difference.

Conclusion: In conclusion, PG analogues are increasingly being prescribed as monotherapy by glaucoma specialists. However, given that our findings support the high frequency of ocular surface illness, practitioners shouldn't be unduly comforted by this.

INTRODUCTION

If treatment is not received, glaucoma, a chronic progressive optic neuropathy, can result in

blindness. It causes a progressive loss of retinal ganglion cells and retinal nerve fiber layers. The goal of all currently available therapeutic treatments is to reduce intraocular pressure (IOP) in order to stop or limit the progression of the disease. IOP-lowering eye drops and, more recently, targeted laser trabeculoplasty are the mainstays of the therapy strategy.¹

Manufacturers of multi-dose topical ophthalmic drugs are required to incorporate antimicrobial preservation systems. Clinicians have long known that prolonged exposure to some preservatives can have harmful side effects in addition to the safety benefits of reduced risk of eye infection and prolonged usage.¹ Both in vitro and in vivo models have been used to show these effects on humans and animals.² Research has also shown that topical treatments containing preservatives exhibit lower levels of ocular toxicity when compared to their non-preserved counterparts. This suggests a clear link between preservative presence and ocular surface damage.³

Benzalkonium chloride is one of the more widely used preservatives nowadays (BAK). Because it can damage cell membranes and accelerate cell death, BAK, a quaternary ammonium molecule, has antibacterial properties. In addition to its antibacterial properties, BAK is toxic to the stroma, conjunctival epithelium, and corneal epithelium.⁴ These alterations seem to be time- and dose-dependent. The total amount of BAK that can be administered over a period of years of repeated drops makes these dangerous side effects very important for treating glaucoma sufferers. Alternative preservatives, such as oxidizing agents like SofZia™, which comprises sorbitol, zinc, and borate, have been introduced. Compared to detergent preservatives like BAK, oxidizing agents might cause less cell harm.^{5,6}

The main purpose of our study was to describe how prostaglandin analog treatment affected the ocular surface of people with glaucoma.

METHODOLOGY:

From January to June 2025, the Armed Forces Institute of Ophthalmology, Rawalpindi, Punjab,

Pakistan, conducted this cross-sectional study. The hospital ethical review board gave its approval. Patients who were above the age of eighteen and taking topical PG analogue monotherapy for glaucoma without a h/o glaucoma surgery, which includes laser techniques and/or minimally invasive glaucoma surgery, were eligible. There was no need for a minimum amount of therapy time prior to enrollment. Therefore, patients undergoing dual or triple therapy, and those who had previously undergone glaucoma surgery were not included.

The baseline tear break-up time (TBUT) for each patient was less than 6 seconds. During the trial time, patients were advised not to apply any additional topical drops. During each visit, the same exam room was used to take baseline measurements of TBUT, inferior corneal staining, and the ocular surface disease index (OSDI).

To make TBUT, five microliters of sodium fluorescein (NaFl) with no preservatives were given to the inferior fornix using a fixed-volume micropipette. The person was urged to blink three times so that the NaFl would mix completely with the tear film. A timer was used to time the first break in the fluorescein-stained tear film, and cobalt blue light was used to set the slit lamp to 16x magnification.

The timer was started right after the last blink and ended when the first fluorescein break happened. We did this three times in a succession, and the average of the three TBUTs was used to figure out the final TBUT. The same person (MYK) used the same method to collect each TBUT at the 8-week follow-up. The inferior corneal staining was rated on a scale from 0 to 4 at the beginning and end of the study. The participants filled out the OSDI questionnaire for the first time and again eight weeks later. Only information from one eye was gathered for every patient. One eye was included if just one eye met the eligibility requirements (that is, all inclusion criteria were met without any ophthalmological exclusion criteria). If both eyes qualified, only the one with the more damaged ocular surface was included. This was defined as the eye with the lowest TBUT or, if that wasn't possible, the one with the worse corneal staining. The right eye was chosen at random to be the worse eye if the two parameters were similar. One researcher

centralized, digitized, and examined the anonymised data.

The SPSS 27.0 was used to do statistical analysis. Means and standard deviations (SD) were used to characterize quantitative variables across the entire population, whereas frequency numbers and percentages were used to characterize qualitative factors. The non-parametric Mann-Whitney test was used to compare quantitative variables. When a p-value was less than 0.05, statistical significance was taken into consideration, and a 95% two-sided confidence interval was calculated.

RESULTS:

The data analysis comprised all 40 patients (80 eyes) who finished the final evaluation of the trial. Age range was 40 to 80 years with mean age of 64.76 ±

8.76 years. Out of 40 patients 26 (65.0%) were males and 14 (35.0%) were females with male to female ratio of 1.8:1. Distribution of patients with other confounding variables is shown in Table I. The 40 eyes under study had a mean TBUT of 2.02 ± 0.71 seconds before beginning prostaglandin analog therapy. Eight weeks following the therapy, this rose to 6.34 ± 1.31 seconds (p < 0.001). The staining of inferior corneas dropped from 2.40 ± 0.87 to 1.38 ± 0.59 (p < 0.001). The initial OSDI reading was 26.31 ± 8.25 and 16.56 ± 6.19 eight weeks after prostaglandin analog therapy. The baseline intraocular pressure (IOP) levels (14.05 ± 2.78 mmHg) and those measured after prostaglandin analog treatment (13.95 ± 3.04, p = 0.88) did not exhibit a statistically significant difference (Table II).

Table II: Distribution of patients with other confounding variables (n=40)

		Frequency	%age
Age (years)	40-60	18	45.0
	61-80	22	55.0
Gender	Male	26	65.0
	Female	14	35.0
Glaucoma Severity	Mild	16	40.0
	Moderate	11	27.50
	Severe	13	32.50

Table-I: Comparison of the impact of prostaglandin analog treatment on glaucoma patients' ocular surfaces.

	Before treatment	Post-therapy	p-value
	Mean ± SD	Mean ± SD	
TUBT (seconds)	2.02 ± 0.71	6.34 ± 1.31	0.0001
Corneal staining	2.40 ± 0.87	1.38 ± 0.59	0.0001
OSDI	26.31 ± 8.25	16.56 ± 6.19	0.0001
IOP (mmHg)	14.05 ± 2.78	13.95 ± 3.04	0.88

DISCUSSION:

According to this study, the great majority of PG analogue monotherapies do not contain preservatives. Compared to certain other European nations, this prescription trend is far higher. For instance, in England, a publicly available prescription cost analysis of primary

care prescriptions revealed that PF prescriptions rose annually starting in 2009 but only reached 13.9% by 2018.⁷ However, a recent study that evaluated the prescribing practices of ocular hypotensive medications in a Spanish public hospital revealed results that were comparable to

ours.⁸ Latanoprost was also one of the most prescribed medications in their survey, and the number of PF PG prescriptions increased from 20% in 2013 to 85% in 2020. The healthcare systems of each nation, the accessibility, cost, and reimbursement status of PF substitutes on the market, as well as regional regulations, may all contribute to the disparity in prescription practices.⁹

The European Medicines Agency (EMA) recommended in a 2009 statement that patients on long-term treatment and those who cannot tolerate eye drops containing preservatives should not use them. As a result, the European Glaucoma Society's most recent guidelines propose PF eyedrops for individuals with glaucoma or OHT who also have an ocular surface condition.¹⁰ While only 20% of patients in our study exhibited clinically significant ocular surface issues prior to treatment with PF-PG analogues.

Raising awareness among glaucoma experts regarding the role of the ocular surface in their treated patients was another goal of this study. Our findings appear to support the necessity of a comprehensive assessment of each glaucomatous patient's ocular surface both before treatment begins and throughout follow-up care. When treated with PG analogues, nearly 80% of patients experienced at least one dry eye sign or symptom; however, only one in three were utilizing artificial tears at the same time. It's important to remember that subjective and objective clinical findings of the condition don't always match up¹¹, even though only 40.7% of patients said they had dry eye symptoms. This is especially true if the patient is getting preserved eyedrops, which can make the cornea more neurotoxic and inflamed and cause few symptoms while making the ocular surface more damaged.¹² In addition to paying close attention to patients' symptoms, a thorough clinical examination of the ocular surface may encourage topical therapy adherence and boost treatment effectiveness.¹³ In practical practice, a drop of fluorescein is frequently enough to evaluate the ocular surface in a matter of minutes, and it is necessary to quantify IOP by applanation.

The aim of this observational real-life study was to enhance awareness of this often-overlooked issue by capturing images of the ocular surface of the treated population. Nevertheless, contingent upon the criterion under evaluation, our subgroup analysis suggests an equivalent or superior tolerance profile of PF eyedrops. Nevertheless, only conjunctival hyperemia, irrespective of treatment duration, reached statistical significance, exhibiting an eightfold elevation in the chance of moderate hyperemia with continued therapy. This outcome is in line with research showing preservatives have harmful effects on the conjunctiva. In fact, preservatives affect conjunctival cells, especially goblet cells, in ways that are oxidative, pro-inflammatory, and pro-apoptotic.¹⁴ Inflammation of the ocular surface is at least partially responsible for the hyperemia connected to PG analogues, even though some of this is due to their vasodilatory impact, which is often temporary.¹⁵ Furthermore, the effectiveness of glaucoma filtering surgery is compromised by this protracted conjunctival inflammation and goblet cell loss, which increases the chance of subconjunctival fibrosis after surgery and, consequently, the prognosis for glaucoma.¹⁶

However, given the study's methodology and the variations in the two groups' sex ratios and treatment durations, these results comparing preserved and PF eyedrops should be carefully interpreted. Women may have been more likely to switch to PF eyedrops because of the increased prevalence and complaints of dry eye illness in this demographic.¹⁷ However, clinical findings may be impacted by gender-related factors in medication adherence.¹⁸ Furthermore, the percentage of patients who had dry eyes prior to starting treatment was probably higher in the PF group and the fact that it was recommended by glaucoma experts. These excipients may be partly or completely responsible for the side effects seen in the PF group.^{19,20}

There are several restrictions on this study. As previously stated, the findings only represent the prescribing practices of glaucoma experts. More

research with a larger sample of prescribers would be required to more accurately determine the general mindset of Pakistani ophthalmologists. It was also hard to definitively determine the time interval between the development of ocular surface diseases and the start of PG analogue treatment because this investigation was cross-sectional. The type of glaucoma was not gathered either.

CONCLUSION:

In conclusion, PG analogues are increasingly being prescribed as monotherapy by glaucoma specialists. However, given that our findings support the high frequency of ocular surface illness, practitioners shouldn't be unduly comforted by this. As a result, it is advised that all glaucoma patients undergo a thorough examination of their ocular surface both during their follow-up and before to starting any topical medicine. For long-term tolerance, adherence, efficacy, and even surgical success, it is crucial to take into account the patient's ocular surface because glaucoma is a chronic condition that requires lifelong therapy. When available, PG formulations having the lowest toxicity to the cornea and conjunctiva should be utilized.

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